

THE ROLE OF ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR IN MEDIATING THE INFLUENCE OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE (Case Study at PT Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Kupang Branch Office)

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the influence of organizational culture and organizational commitment on employee performance with Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) as a mediating variable at PT Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Kupang Branch Office. This study uses a quantitative method with an associative approach. The sample was determined by a non-probability sampling technique on BNI Kupang Branch employees. Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires to 118 respondents. Data analysis used Partial Least Square (PLS) with the help of SmartPLS 4.0 software. The results of the study indicate that: (1) Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance; (2) Organizational commitment does not have a significant effect on employee performance; (3) Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on OCB; (4) Organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on OCB; (5) OCB has a positive and significant effect on employee performance; (6) OCB partially mediates the effect of organizational culture on employee performance; and (7) OCB fully mediates the effect of organizational commitment on employee performance. Consistent with previous research, these results confirm that organizational culture is a crucial factor in enhancing employee OCB. Practically, these findings provide implications for BNI Kupang Branch that employee performance improvements can be achieved by strengthening organizational culture, organizational commitment, and consistently encouraging OCB behavior.

Keywords: *Organizational citizenship behavior, organizational culture, organizational commitment, employee performance.*

INTRODUCTION

Increasing competition in various economic sectors, driven by globalization, requires industry players to adapt their behavior, methods, and business strategies to maintain their existence and sustainability. Adaptability to respond to changes in the company's internal and external environments is absolutely necessary, given that the environment is one of the dominant factors determining a company's sustainability and competitive advantage (Ali et al., 2022). An organization will struggle to maintain its business sustainability or improve the welfare of its members if member behaviors that reflect 'good citizen' behavior are not considered in its activities or in the development of organizational strategies. One factor influencing an organization's success rate is performance. According to (Manora et al., 2021b), employee performance is a condition that must be known and confirmed to certain parties to determine the level of achievement of an agency's results related to the company's vision and to understand the positive and negative impacts of operational policies. Every agency/organization always strives to improve employee performance in the hope that goals will be achieved as expected by the agency/organization. Employee performance plays a very important role in an agency. If an agency has good human resources and high performance, then the agency's goals can be achieved. One factor influencing an organization's success rate is performance. According to (Manora et al., 2021b), employee performance is a condition that must be known and confirmed to certain parties to determine the level of achievement of an agency's results related to the company's vision and to understand the positive and negative impacts of an operational policy. Every agency/organization

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always strives to improve employee performance in the hope that goals will be achieved as expected by the agency/organization. Employee performance plays a very important role in an agency. If an agency has good human resources and high performance, then the agency's goals can achieve the goals expected by the agency/organization (Irmayanti, Widiastini, & Suarmanayasa, 2020; Aditya & Suarmanayasa, 2024). One factor influencing employee performance is organizational culture. Organizational culture is a set of values that govern interactions between individuals within an organization, other organizations as suppliers, and members of the community it serves. Organizational culture is shaped by the individuals within the organization, the organization's ethics, the employee rights granted to each employee, and the type of organizational structure itself (Othman et al., 2005). Research (Aggarwal & Mittal, 2021) shows that organizational culture has a positive and significant impact on employee performance. From these research results, it can be concluded that if the organizational culture provided by an agency to employees is appropriate, it will foster good employee performance that can work effectively and efficiently as expected by the agency (Irmayanti et al., 2020).

Organizational commitment also influences employee performance. According to (Simanjuntak et al., 2020), organizational commitment is an employee's attitude of loyalty to the organization, through remaining with the organization, helping achieve organizational goals, and having no desire to leave the organization for any reason. Commitment is a form of identification, loyalty, and involvement expressed by employees towards the organization. Employees who are committed to the organization will demonstrate positive behavior and attitudes towards their organization, thus feeling happy at work. Employees will carry out their duties and obligations well, which is ultimately expected to provide service and satisfaction to external consumers. This can be seen from the results of research (Manora et al., 2021a) stating that organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance (Billah, Suci, & Suarmanayasa, 2022). In addition to organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behavior also influences employee performance. Organizational citizenship behavior is defined as employee behavior that goes above and beyond assigned duties, whether or not it is performed freely, is recognized through formal organizational rewards, and contributes to organizational effectiveness. In other words, organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) is an employee's behavior not driven by job demands, but rather by voluntary and voluntary values (Sumardjo & Supriadi, 2023). Research (Grego-Planer, 2019) indicates that organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) has a positive and significant impact on employee performance (Wiranata, Sinarwati, & Rahmawati, 2022).

Employee performance is one of the factors that determine an organization's success in achieving strategic goals. Organizations need human resources who are not only capable of completing formal tasks but also willing to make extra contributions beyond their job descriptions. This voluntary work behavior is known as Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), which has been proven to increase organizational effectiveness by enhancing collaboration, productivity, and service quality. Previous research has shown that internal organizational factors such as organizational culture and organizational commitment play a significant role in shaping employee work behavior and performance. A strong organizational culture is believed to shape values, norms, and behavioral patterns that encourage employees to work more disciplined and proactively. This is in line with the findings of Irmayanti et al. (2020), which show that work culture influences performance through the formation of positive work behaviors. (Fatmawati et al., 2022) also strengthens these findings by stating that leadership and competence created from a good work culture can improve employee performance (Billah et al., 2022).

Organizational commitment is also a crucial factor influencing performance. Employees with high commitment tend to demonstrate loyalty, a sense of belonging, and a willingness to contribute more, including volunteer behaviors such as OCB. Research (Vridyaningtyas, 2022) confirms that psychological components such as harmonious leadership and personality influence employee performance, as demonstrated in the context of educational organizations and the public sector (Billah et al., 2022). Similar results were found by (Fadly et al., 2021), who stated that discipline and motivation influence the performance of public sector employees (Aditya & Suarmanayasa, 2024). Several other studies emphasize the importance of motivation and the work environment in influencing performance. (Sarmila et al., 2019) showed that motivation and work discipline significantly influence employee performance. Similar findings were obtained by (Suryani et al., 2023), who found a positive relationship between motivation and work discipline and improved employee performance, in line with the results of research by Aditya and Suarmanayasa (2024). Furthermore, research (Anwar, 2021) also supports that work competence and motivation can improve employee performance (Irmayanti et al., 2020). OCB plays a crucial role as a bridging factor between organizational variables and performance. According to Sutarjo et al., 2021, psychological conditions such as job stress and satisfaction contribute to improved performance through voluntary extra-curricular behavior. Marlina et al., 2020, explain that implementing OCB can create a work environment that supports team harmony

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and effectiveness. In the education and public service sectors, research (Said et al., 2021) shows that talent management and motivation influence the performance of non-civil servant employees (Manuaba, Rahmawati, & Suarmanayasa, 2025). Meanwhile, Fan et al., 2023 found that career development can improve performance by increasing work readiness and positive work behavior (Risadiana, Widiastini, & Rahmawati, 2025). BNI has played a significant role in supporting national economic development. With various services such as corporate financing, small and medium enterprises (SMEs), and retail services, BNI continues to innovate to meet community needs and support government programs. To date, BNI is known as one of the largest banks in Indonesia with an extensive network, both domestically and internationally. With the tagline "Serving the Country, Pride of the Nation", BNI remains committed to providing the best service and supporting Indonesia's economic growth. PT Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Kupang Branch Office is one of the operational units of PT Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. located in Kupang, NTT. As part of one of the largest and oldest banks in Indonesia, BNI Kupang Branch plays a vital role in providing banking services to the local community, including individuals and businesses. This branch office offers a variety of banking products and services, ranging from savings and loans to investment services. With a focus on customer service and product development that suits local market needs, BNI Kupang Branch is committed to supporting regional economic growth. To support service continuity and achieve business targets, the presence of high-performing human resources is crucial. However, based on initial observations and direct interviews conducted by the author with several employees at the branch office, employee performance remains a key issue requiring improvement, *particularly* in terms of productivity and service effectiveness.

Based on performance data as of March 2025, several key indicators show that BNI Kupang's performance is still below the set target. Third Party Funds (DPK) growth only reached 0.21%, or 95.15% of the March proportional target and 82.68% of the *full-year target*. Meanwhile, credit performance recorded growth of 1.48%, or 98.18% of the March 2025 proportional target and only 89.46% of the 2025 *full-year target*. The productivity of the marketing staff has not shown optimal results, where of the 27 marketing staff owned by BNI Kupang Branch, only 11 were able to achieve productivity above 100%. Likewise, in terms of service quality, the Kupang Branch's Service Quality Index (SQI) as of December 2024 was at 3.8, out of the target of 5, placing BNI Kupang in 7th place out of 9 branches in the Denpasar area. This condition in aggregate indicates that the effectiveness of work and internal synergy at the Kupang Branch is still not fully optimal. The results of the author's interviews with several employees of the BNI Kupang Branch, from assistant to manager levels, indicate that the root of performance issues does not solely originate from technical aspects, but is also closely related to organizational culture and commitment to company values. BNI has a work culture value of AKHLAK, namely Trustworthy, Competent, Harmonious, Loyal, Adaptive, and Collaborative, but its implementation at the branch is still inconsistent. There are several work cultures that need special attention at the Kupang Branch to be improved, including:

1. Collaboration :

Collaboration between units within the company remains suboptimal in a small portion of the company. These silos hinder processes and hinder target achievement. Work patterns need to be improved, with each individual actively working together to achieve common goals. In this culture, the primary value lies not in individual abilities, but in how everyone contributes, supports each other, and shares ideas for better results.

2. *Agile and Innovative*

A culture of waiting for direction/instructions from superiors when carrying out a *project*. There's a lack of initiative and confidence in expressing ideas/innovations. Employee militancy and innovation are lacking. They still work based on established habits, and *after-sales activities* are generally substandard.

3. Consistency and Responsibility:

Consistency and accountability from each employee are still lacking. For example, *daily activity input* requires daily reminders, and there's a lack of *awareness* of individual targets that should be achieved.

4. *Comfort zone* :

Many employees are comfortable in their positions and do not want to move and develop.

The conclusion regarding BNI Kupang Branch's commitment to employees is that BNI has a mission to create the best conditions for employees, providing a place of pride for work and achievement. The implementation of career fairness for all BNI Kupang Branch employees is considered to be running well. Career opportunities and opportunities are widely open to employees through a fair and transparent selection system. There is no discrimination based on position, age, gender, or personal affiliation. The provision of *rewards* and *punishments* has also been running well, not only periodically but also become a daily culture in the work by always giving appreciation, both verbally and in the form of gifts or job promotions to employees who excel. Punishment *is* also given consistently to employees according to the results of their respective performance, with prior *coaching* and

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mentoring as well as guidance for employees who *underperform* or employees who have taken an action that does not comply with the provisions. This has an impact on employees feeling appreciated and motivated, thus emerging a sense of belonging (*sense of belonging*) to the Company. However, there are still differing opinions, where *rewards* and *punishments* are still considered *biased*. The implementation of *rewards* is assessed solely based on the final value/score of an indicator. The hope is to also assess the overall sustainability of the indicator. For career fairness, attention must be paid to employees who remain at the same grade after four years of service or more. Regarding the implementation of OCB at BNI Kupang, respondents' opinions were as follows: OCB has been running well at BNI Kupang, but not all employees yet embrace the culture. Examples include helping colleagues without being asked and taking the initiative to find solutions when the team encounters obstacles. They believe that when the company is fair in careers, rewards, and sanctions, employees will feel valued and treated with respect. This fosters a strong affective commitment, encouraging them to help colleagues and contribute beyond their formal responsibilities to the company. They emphasized that a positive mentality and inspiring leadership are important factors in improving branch performance. Strong management support is also a key driver of work motivation.

The interview results indicate that the main challenges facing BNI Kupang Branch lie in a work culture that is not yet fully collaborative and proactive, inconsistencies in the implementation of organizational values, and the need for strengthened leadership at the operational level. Although the reward system and organizational commitment have been running well, there are still gaps in perception and practice in the field. OCB, which is the pillar of creating superior performance, has not been implemented consistently by all employees, and this has impacted the overall performance of the branch. Based on these conditions, it can be stated that employee performance at BNI Kupang Branch is influenced by various interrelated factors, namely organizational culture, organizational commitment, and OCB behavior. To improve performance sustainably, comprehensive interventions are needed in the form of strengthening a collaborative work culture, increasing participatory leadership, and enforcing a fair reward and career system. Thus, it is expected that employees can work with high motivation, behave extra-role, and contribute more to the achievement of the company's strategic goals. Therefore, this study was conducted to empirically examine the role of *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* as a mediating variable between organizational culture and organizational commitment to employee performance at PT Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Kupang Branch.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee performance is a crucial indicator of an organization's effectiveness in achieving its established strategic goals. Performance reflects an individual's ability to complete tasks inherent in their role according to established standards, targets, and responsibilities. Performance assessments are not solely quantitative but also consider output quality, timeliness, collaborative skills, and professional behavior in carrying out tasks (Oktafianus et al., 2022). Performance achievement is influenced by internal factors such as competence, experience, discipline, and motivation, as well as external factors such as a supportive work environment. Therefore, organizations need to implement an objective performance management system, accompanied by ongoing training and constructive feedback, to create a systematic and sustainable development process. In the service context, employee performance is also influenced by work ethic, customer orientation, and willingness to contribute beyond formal obligations. With optimal performance, organizations can maintain a competitive advantage, increase customer satisfaction, and build a sustainable reputation.

Organizational culture plays a central role in shaping employee work behavior and performance. Organizational culture is defined as a system of values, beliefs, norms, and habits collectively held by members of an organization, which guides daily attitudes and actions (Ishak et al., 2022). A strong culture is reflected through consistent work patterns, communication, decision-making, and problem-solving. Cultural elements such as leadership style, symbols, rituals, traditions, and organizational stories gradually shape a collective identity that distinguishes one organization from another. A healthy organizational culture encourages innovation, openness, collaboration, and commitment to achieving results. When an organization's core values are understood and internalized by all members, behavioral alignment is created that strengthens the organization's strategic direction. Conversely, a weak or inconsistent culture has the potential to create conflict, resistance, and reduce work motivation. Effective implementation of organizational culture is achieved through leadership role models, strengthening a fair reward and punishment system, intensive communication, and adapting to environmental changes. A strong organizational culture has been proven not only to improve employee performance but also to strengthen organizational loyalty, coordination, and sustainability.

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Organizational commitment is also a significant determinant of employee performance. Organizational commitment reflects an employee's level of psychological attachment to the organization, which motivates them to continue contributing optimally (Muhaimin et al., 2021). Commitment encompasses not only loyalty but also an individual's identification with the organization's values and a willingness to actively participate in achieving shared goals. Employees with high commitment tend to feel pride in their work, feel a sense of belonging, and are less likely to consider moving to another organization. Human resource management theory divides organizational commitment into three dimensions: affective commitment (emotional attachment), normative commitment (a sense of moral obligation), and continuance commitment (consideration of the costs of leaving the organization). Strengthening commitment can be achieved through a supportive work environment, a fair reward and promotion system, career development opportunities, and positive interpersonal relationships. When employees' psychological needs—including recognition, trust, and security—are met, organizational commitment grows significantly. High commitment positively impacts performance improvement, reduced absenteeism, and employee retention. Therefore, developing organizational commitment is an investment strategy in creating productive, stable, and long-term-oriented human resources (Sari et al., 2021).

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is a behavioral dimension that contributes to organizational performance through voluntary actions beyond formal employee obligations. OCB includes a willingness to help coworkers, maintain a conducive work environment, improve service quality, and provide constructive ideas for organizational progress. The presence of OCB reflects employees' emotional involvement and sense of concern for the organization. Factors influencing OCB include job satisfaction, organizational commitment, leadership, organizational culture, and perceptions of fairness (Rismayadi & Maemunah, 2016). Employees who experience trust and fair treatment are more likely to exhibit prosocial behavior that facilitates team coordination and collaboration. OCB plays a crucial role in improving organizational efficiency, as many critical activities can be carried out through employee initiatives that are not listed in formal job descriptions. Organizations with high levels of OCB are generally more adaptive, resilient, and able to cope with the dynamics of changing business environments. Therefore, companies need to create a work culture that supports active participation, values extra-role contributions, and provides space for continuous employee competency development.

METHOD

The research approach used in this study is associative with quantitative methods because the main objective is to explain and test the relationship between statistically measurable variables. The variables studied include organizational culture (X1) and organizational commitment (X2) as independent variables, organizational citizenship behavior (Z) as an intervening variable, and employee performance (Y) as the dependent variable. All variables are operationalized into measurable indicators based on expert theories so that they can be assessed using a Likert-scale questionnaire instrument. A population of all 118 employees of BNI Kupang Branch was used as a research sample using census techniques to obtain a comprehensive picture of the organizational condition. Primary data were collected through interviews and questionnaires, then tested for quality through validity and reliability tests. Path analysis was applied to test the direct and indirect influences between variables so that the hypothesis can be empirically proven and support the solution of the research problem.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data analysis

Direct Effect Hypothesis Testing

Table 1. Testing the Direct Effect Hypothesis

No	Influence between Variables	Coefficient	T-Stat	P-Values	Hypothesis
1	Organizational Culture (X1) → Employee Performance (Y)	0.477	7,404	0,000	H ₁ accepted
2	Organizational Commitment (X2) → Employee Performance (Y)	0.106	1,057	0.291	H ₂ is rejected
3	Organizational Culture (X1) → OCB (Z)	0.485	6,527	0,000	H ₃ accepted
4	Organizational Commitment (X2) → OCB (Z)	0.460	6,997	0,000	H ₄ accepted
5	OCB (Z) → Employee Performance (Y)	0.318	3,328	0.001	H ₅ accepted

Based on Table 1 above, it can be explained as follows:

1. The results of the first hypothesis test indicate that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance (H₁ is accepted). This is indicated by a coefficient value of 0.477, with a t-statistic value of 7.404 and a p-value of 0.000, which is far below the significance limit of 0.05. This means that the better the organizational culture perceived by employees, which includes aspects of ability, management attention, social interaction, order, and trust, the higher the level of performance demonstrated by employees. Thus, a strong and positive organizational culture is an important factor in encouraging increased productivity and work effectiveness of employees in this branch office environment.
2. The results of the second hypothesis test indicate that organizational commitment does not significantly influence employee performance (H₂ is rejected). The coefficient of influence is 0.106, with a t-statistic of 1.057 and a p-value of 0.291, which is greater than the significance threshold of 0.05. This indicates that the level of emotional attachment, loyalty, and sense of belonging of employees to the organization have not been able to provide a significant direct contribution to improving performance. In other words, although employees feel committed to the organization, this is not strong enough to directly drive performance.
3. The third hypothesis test shows that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on OCB (H₃ is accepted), with a coefficient value of 0.485, a t-statistic of 6.527, and a p-value of 0.000. This result means that the stronger the organizational culture created, the higher the tendency of employees to display extra-role behaviors that support the organization, such as helping coworkers, being disciplined, and caring about the company's progress. A positive organizational culture has been proven to be able to encourage the formation of voluntary work behavior that supports the overall effectiveness of the organization.
4. The results of the fourth hypothesis test indicate that organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on OCB (H₄ is accepted), with a coefficient of 0.460, a t-statistic of 6.997, and a p-value of 0.000. These results indicate that employees who have a high sense of pride, loyalty, and concern for the organization tend to exhibit positive behaviors that go beyond formal obligations. High commitment encourages employees to contribute voluntarily to the success of the organization, such as working overtime without being asked or actively helping coworkers. Thus, organizational commitment is an important factor in fostering OCB behavior in the workplace.
5. The fifth hypothesis test shows that OCB has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, with a coefficient of 0.318, a t-statistic of 3.328, and a p-value of 0.001. This result indicates that the higher the OCB behavior demonstrated by employees, the higher the level of performance achieved. Voluntary extra-role behavior by employees has been shown to contribute directly to improving employee performance.

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Indirect Effect Hypothesis Testing

Table 2 Testing the Hypothesis of Mediation Effect

No	Influence between Variables	Coefficient	T-Stat	P-Values	Hypothesis
1	Organizational Culture (X1) →OCB (Z) →Employee Performance (Y)	0.154	2,937	0.003	H ₆ received
2	Organizational Commitment (X2) →OCB (Z) →Employee Performance (Y)	0.146	2,933	0.003	H ₇ accepted

Table 2 shows the indirect effect of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance mediated by *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* (OCB) with a path coefficient of 0.154, a T-statistic value = 2.937 and a P-value of 0.003. The path coefficient value of 0.154 means that the indirect effect of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance mediated by *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* (OCB) is positive at 0.154. The T-statistic value = 2.937 > 1.96 and P-value = 0.003 < 0.05 means that the indirect effect of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance mediated by *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* (OCB) is significant.

Discussion

The Influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance

The research results shown in Table 4.10 show that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Kupang Branch Office, with a probability value (p-value) of 0.000. This finding confirms the H1 hypothesis that the better the organizational culture perceived by employees, the higher the level of performance they demonstrate. Empirically, these results emphasize that organizational values function as a guide for work behavior that has a direct impact on improving the quality, quantity, and accuracy of employee work completion (Sutrisno, 2018; Wirawan, 2017; Sulaksono, 2015). This finding is also in line with the summary of performance evaluation results that show variations in productivity between employees, where employees with better perceptions of work culture generally show higher performance (Gultom, 2014; Arianty, 2014).

These statistical findings align with the field reality revealed through initial observations and in-depth interviews with BNI Kupang Branch employees. In practice, the implementation of BNI's work culture through AKHLAK values is not yet fully consistent across all work units. Interviews revealed issues of inter-unit collaboration, a tendency to work within comfort zones, low initiative, and a lack of consistency in job responsibilities. This condition reflects that the suboptimal internalization of organizational culture has the potential to create differences in work behavior and performance among employees (Ardiana et al., 2013; Lina, 2014; Hadijaya, 2020). This situation is reflected in branch performance indicators, such as Third Party Funds (DPK) achievement of only 95.15% of the proportional target and a Service Quality Index (SQI) that ranks 7th out of 9 branches. Employees who demonstrate better discipline, collaboration, and initiative tend to have higher productivity, as evidenced by only 11 of 27 marketers achieving productivity above 100%. Thus, field data makes it clear that a strong organizational culture is an important foundation for achieving business targets and improving individual performance (Jufrizen & Rahmadhani, 2020; Muis et al., 2018).

The findings of this study are consistent with previous literature stating that organizational culture is a crucial factor in improving employee performance. Wulandari and Ratnawati (2019) emphasized that a strong organizational culture shapes employee behavior and creates a conducive work environment for improved performance. Ningrum and Purnamasari (2022) also demonstrated that organizational culture influences employee resource allocation, innovation, and proactive attitudes, which contribute to business excellence. These findings are reinforced by research by Abdurrahman (2021), Arianty (2012), and Andayani and Tirtayasa (2019), which agree that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on performance. Therefore, the research findings at the BNI Kupang Branch are not only supported by internal empirical findings but also based on theoretical consistency and strong empirical evidence from previous studies.

The Influence of Organizational Commitment on Employee Performance

The results of the study in Table 1 show that organizational commitment has a positive but insignificant effect on employee performance at PT Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Kupang Branch Office, with a

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probability value (p-value) of 0.291. Thus, the hypothesis H2 which states that organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance is rejected. This finding indicates that increased organizational commitment perceived by employees does not automatically result in increased performance (Mathis & Jackson, 2012; Yusuf & Syarif, 2018). In the operational context of BNI Kupang Branch, these results indicate that employee commitment to the organization has not been a determining factor in achieving individual performance, even though the company has attempted to implement a structured career and reward system (Samsuddin, 2018; Risnawati, 2016).

These results align with empirical conditions in the field, which indicate that employee commitment perceptions are more transactional than affective. Demographic analysis in Table 4.3 shows that the majority of respondents are aged 21–30 (50%) and 31–40 (39.8%). This age group, which represents millennials and early Generation Z, tends to have a more volatile commitment orientation based on career development opportunities, work flexibility, and work-life balance, rather than long-term loyalty (Kristine, 2017; Kusumapuri, 2018). Furthermore, the homogeneous educational composition, dominated by bachelor's degree graduates (80.5%), reflects the characteristics of a modern workforce oriented toward career mobility and professional development (Indasari et al., 2018; Nofriansyah, 2018). Field observations indicate that employees prioritize compensation systems, fairness of rewards, direct leadership, and career advancement opportunities over emotional attachment to the organization (Bahri, 2018; Jufrizen et al., 2017). This explains why organizational commitment, although generally in the fairly good category, is not strong enough to influence work behavior or drive significant performance improvements (Nadapdap, 2017; Shaleh, 2018).

This research finding is supported by previous studies that also found that organizational commitment does not always have a significant effect on performance. Research by Dede Hardani et al. (2023) showed that organizational commitment does not significantly contribute to improving employee performance. Similar results were also revealed by Maharani and Vembriati (2019) who found that high or low organizational commitment does not affect work performance, especially when employees prioritize compensation, reward systems, or other more instrumental factors. The literature on organizational behavior also confirms that organizational commitment can lose its driving force for performance when it is not accompanied by a fair reward system, effective leadership, and clear career development opportunities (Sutrisno, 2018; Busro, 2018). Contemporary literature on the workforce behavior of the younger generation also explains that their commitment tends to be pragmatic and dynamic, so it does not always correlate with work behavior or work outcomes (Sugianingrat et al., 2021; Oganisjana et al., 2023). Thus, the insignificance of organizational commitment in this study does not only come from statistical results, but is also a representation of the commitment pattern of the modern workforce which no longer makes organizational loyalty the main determinant of work performance.

The Influence of Organizational Culture on OCB

The results of the study in Table 4.10 show that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on the *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* (OCB) of employees of PT Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Kupang Branch Office, with a probability value (p-value) of 0.000. Thus, the hypothesis H3 is accepted, which means that the better the implementation of organizational culture in the work environment, the higher the tendency of employees to display extra-role behavior that supports the smooth operation of the organization. This finding confirms that the values, norms, and work patterns built by BNI are able to be the main drivers of the formation of voluntary behavior outside of formal duties which is reflected in OCB (Sutrisno, 2018; Sanhaji et al., 2016; Rini et al., 2013). These statistical findings are consistent with the reality on the ground at the BNI Kupang Branch, where the implementation of AKHLAK cultural values, such as trustworthiness, collaboration, adaptability, and competence, appears to have a tangible impact on employee work behavior.

Interview results indicate that employees frequently display supportive behavior, maintain work ethics, and demonstrate concern for coworkers and customers without waiting for direct instructions from superiors. For example, during long queues or a surge in transactions, employees from other units volunteer to assist with the service process, provide direction to customers, and assist coworkers experiencing high service loads. They also demonstrate *conscientious behavior* by maintaining the tidiness of the service area, ensuring the readiness of work facilities, and contributing to office social activities and company promotions. Behaviors such as *altruism*, *civic virtue*, and *courtesy* demonstrate that a strong work culture has become the foundation for the emergence of collective awareness, a sense of *belonging*, and an informal commitment to support overall branch operations (Husodo, 2018; Putra et al., 2018; Nisa et al., 2018). Theoretically, these findings align with the view of Syaifullah et al. (2019) who stated that a strong organizational culture can encourage employees to exhibit behaviors outside of

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formal job descriptions as a form of contribution to achieving organizational goals. Organizational culture is understood as a system of values, beliefs, and norms that guide the behavior of organizational members in facing operational situations. When these values are well internalized, employees are encouraged to demonstrate OCB behaviors such as helping coworkers, maintaining organizational stability, and actively participating in internal activities (Dewanggana et al., 2016; Nadeak, 2016). Zaluchu (2019) also emphasized that the implementation of a strong organizational culture will create a conducive work environment that increases OCB and performance. The results of this study are also consistent with the empirical findings of Hiariej and Manuputty (2023), as well as research by Maulani et al. (2015) and Lestari and Ghaby (2018), which concluded that organizational culture has a positive and significant influence on OCB. The consistency of these findings indicates that organizational culture is a fundamental factor that shapes voluntary, proactive, and collective contribution-oriented behavior in banking organizations such as BNI.

The Influence of Organizational Commitment on OCB

The results of the study in Table 1 show that organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) among employees of PT Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Kupang Branch Office, with a probability value (p-value) of 0.000. Thus, hypothesis H4 is accepted, which means that the higher the level of employee commitment to the organization, the greater their tendency to display voluntary behavior that supports organizational effectiveness. This finding indicates that emotional attachment, sense of responsibility, and employee loyalty to the company have a direct contribution in encouraging extra-role behaviors that are characteristics of OCB (Toding et al., 2023; Said et al., 2021). These findings align with the real-world conditions within the BNI Kupang Branch. Interviews and observations indicate that employees with high organizational commitment tend to demonstrate a willingness to contribute beyond their formal duties. They volunteer to assist coworkers facing high service loads, maintain order and tidiness in service areas, and remain actively involved in office activities, both operational and social. Employees with strong loyalty also demonstrate high discipline, a high level of compliance with company regulations, and a sense of responsibility to uphold BNI's reputation in every interaction with customers.

Behaviors such as spontaneous assistance (altruism), maintaining work quality (conscientiousness), and active involvement in organizational activities (civic virtue) are direct reflections of strong organizational commitment (Subiyanto & Utami, 2021). All of these behaviors demonstrate that commitment not only influences internal attitudes but also generates tangible contributions that support teamwork harmony and overall branch performance. Theoretically, the results of this study align with the view of Toding et al. (2023), who stated that organizational commitment reflects employees' psychological and physical attachment to the organization, which encourages them to exhibit positive behaviors beyond formal job demands. Employees with high commitment tend to show pride in the organization and are encouraged to engage in extra-role behaviors as a form of contribution to organizational goals. These results are consistent with research by Subiyanto and Utami (2021), which emphasized that organizational commitment encourages employees to give their best effort, including helping coworkers and working beyond working hours without expecting rewards. Other previous research findings, such as those by Said et al. (2021), also support that organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on OCB. Thus, the findings of this study are not only empirically supported by field conditions but also consistent with the literature stating that commitment is one of the main predictors of OCB formation in an organizational environment.

The Influence of OCB on Employee Performance

The results of the study in Table 1 show that Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Kupang Branch Office, with a probability value (p-value) of 0.000. Thus, hypothesis H5 is accepted, meaning the higher the level of OCB of employees, the better their performance. This finding confirms that extra-role behaviors, such as helping coworkers, maintaining teamwork harmony, and taking initiatives beyond formal job descriptions, are important factors supporting target achievement and increasing cross-unit work effectiveness within the BNI Kupang Branch (Angraini et al., 2021; Aulia, 2021). These results are highly relevant to real-world conditions. Employees with high levels of OCB not only demonstrate excellent performance in their primary duties but also play an active role in ensuring smooth branch operations. In daily service activities, employees voluntarily assist colleagues when transactions spike, provide guidance to customers without waiting for instructions, and maintain a conducive work environment through mutual respect and cooperation. In the context of customer service, OCB is evident through employees' proactive behavior in providing additional information, explaining service procedures, or helping direct customers

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to relevant units, even though these activities are not part of their formal duties. These behaviors of altruism, courtesy, conscientiousness, and civic virtue directly support a better service experience, strengthen the company's image, and increase the effectiveness of branch operations (Basuki, 2023). With high levels of OCB practices among employees, cross-unit coordination runs more smoothly, workloads can be handled collectively, and service quality improves, ultimately contributing to improved individual and organizational performance. Theoretically, these findings align with the opinion of Angraini et al. (2021), who explained that OCB is voluntary behavior not directly related to a formal reward system, but in aggregate can increase organizational effectiveness. Research by Aulia (2021) also shows that OCB has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, where increased OCB encourages work effectiveness, collaboration, and productivity. Previous research, such as that conducted by Basuki (2023), consistently states that OCB is a key determinant in improving employee performance. Therefore, the results of this study are not only supported by empirical evidence from working conditions at the BNI Kupang Branch but also have a strong theoretical and empirical basis from various previous studies that confirm the positive relationship between OCB and employee performance.

The Influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance Mediated by OCB

The results of the study in Table 2 show that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through OCB as a mediating variable, with a p -value of 0.003 (<0.05). Thus, hypothesis H6 is accepted, meaning OCB significantly mediates the relationship between organizational culture and employee performance at PT Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Kupang Branch Office. This finding indicates that organizational culture not only directly influences performance but also works through increasing employee voluntary behavior. The stronger the organizational culture, the higher the OCB that emerges, and ultimately the better the resulting performance (Hariyanto et al., 2021; Gadzali, 2022).

Empirically, this phenomenon is clearly reflected in operational routines at the BNI Kupang Branch. The implementation of AKHLAK cultural values, such as trustworthiness, competence, harmony, adaptability, and collaboration, encourages positive behaviors aligned with the concept of OCB. Employees demonstrate a strong sense of togetherness, helping each other complete tasks, and maintaining the company's ethics and image in interactions with customers. For example, during times of peak *customer service*, employees from other units volunteer to help direct customers, expedite queues, or provide additional information without being asked by superiors. Furthermore, a culture of discipline and responsibility is evident in employee initiatives to maintain the tidiness of the service area, support product promotions, and participate in social activities. Behaviors such as *altruism*, *conscientiousness*, and *civic virtue* demonstrate that a strong organizational culture creates a work climate conducive to the development of OCB, which then leads to improved individual and team performance (Firmansyah & Zanora, 2021).

The findings of this study align with various previous studies. Hariyanto et al. (2021) demonstrated that OCB acts as a partial mediator in the relationship between organizational culture and employee performance, thus optimizing performance improvement when organizational culture is supported by strong OCB behaviors. Gadzali (2022) also demonstrated the indirect influence of organizational culture on performance through OCB, emphasizing that a strong work culture is more effective in driving performance achievement if it results in voluntary employee behavior. Firmansyah and Zanora's (2021) research even found that the indirect influence of organizational culture on performance through OCB is greater than its direct influence. Theoretically, this can be explained as OCB reflects employee behavior that goes beyond formal demands based on a sense of belonging and commitment to the organization. Therefore, implementing a strong organizational culture is an important foundation for fostering OCB, which ultimately has a positive impact on employee performance.

The Effect of Organizational Commitment on Employee Performance Mediated by OCB

Findings: This study's findings indicate that organizational commitment does not have a significant direct effect on employee performance, as seen in the H2 test results, which showed a p -value of 0.291 (>0.05). In the context of the BNI Kupang Branch, this indicates that employee loyalty, emotional attachment, and desire to remain with the organization are not strong enough to directly improve performance (Sofyanty, 2019). Passive organizational commitment—for example, simply feeling comfortable working at BNI, having a sense of belonging to the company, or not intending to change jobs—does not necessarily translate into increased productivity, service quality, or task completion effectiveness (Salsabila & Hermiana, 2021). This explains why some employees who are loyal to BNI still demonstrate standard work performance, working only on their primary tasks, and are less proactive in supporting the achievement of work unit targets.

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However, the results of the mediation analysis on H7 provide a more comprehensive picture. The results in Table 2 show that organizational commitment has a positive effect on employee performance through OCB as a mediating variable, with a *p-value* of 0.003 (<0.05). Thus, hypothesis H7 is accepted, meaning OCB significantly mediates the relationship between organizational commitment and employee performance at PT Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Kupang Branch Office. This means that organizational commitment still plays a significant role, but this influence is only strongly apparent when it encourages the emergence of extra-role behavior, or OCB. In other words, high commitment will encourage the growth of OCB, and this OCB then improves employee performance more optimally (Agustian et al., 2018; Salsabila & Hermana, 2021).

This phenomenon is clearly visible in operational activities at the BNI Kupang Branch. Employees with a high level of commitment demonstrate a strong willingness to assist colleagues without waiting for instructions from their superiors, especially during times of increased service volume, such as when customer queues are long at the teller or *customer service desk*. Employees voluntarily provide additional information to customers, direct them to the appropriate unit, or expedite the service process to maintain the quality of branch service. Furthermore, employees with strong commitment are also actively involved in informal company activities, such as supporting marketing activities, maintaining a tidy work area, and participating in social and internal company activities. The *altruism*, *civic virtue*, and *conscientiousness behaviors* that emerge from this commitment prove that the higher an employee's commitment to the organization, the greater their tendency to display OCB, which is ultimately reflected in improved individual and team performance (Agustian et al., 2018; Sofyanty, 2019). OCB serves as a link that transforms commitment into concrete, productive actions in branch operations.

The findings of this study align with those of Salsabila and Hermana (2021), who demonstrated that OCB partially mediates the effect of organizational commitment on employee performance, suggesting that performance will improve more effectively if organizational commitment is accompanied by high levels of OCB behavior. Furthermore, research by Agustian et al. (2018) also confirmed that OCB is a voluntary behavior that, although not directly linked to a formal reward system, can increase organizational effectiveness and mediate the effect of commitment on performance. Research by Sofyanty (2019) also consistently demonstrates similar findings, namely that organizational commitment does not always automatically result in high performance but requires behavioral channels in the form of OCB such as helping coworkers, going above and beyond minimum standards, taking initiative, and maintaining a work ethic to make a significant contribution to performance.

Thus, in the context of this research, OCB functions as a mediating mechanism *that* transforms organizational commitment from mere latent loyalty into concrete actions that impact performance improvement. Organizational commitment is not a stand-alone predictor of performance, but rather a psychological capital that only produces optimal impact when expressed through OCB in daily work activities (Salsabila & Hermana, 2021; Sofyanty, 2019). These findings emphasize the importance of fostering a work culture that fosters extra-role behavior so that employee commitment can contribute maximally to achieving the strategic goals of BNI Kupang Branch.

CONCLUSION

The results of the study indicate that strengthening organizational culture plays a crucial role in encouraging optimal employee performance at PT. Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. Kupang Branch Office. This finding confirms that when corporate values are consistently implemented in daily work activities, employees will be more motivated to work professionally, provide the best service, and demonstrate behavior that aligns with organizational goals. A strong organizational culture has been shown to enhance Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), where employees voluntarily contribute more without expecting immediate rewards. This ultimately strengthens the improvement of individual and work unit performance as a whole. Organizational commitment apparently has no direct impact on performance. However, commitment remains important because through increased OCB, its positive effects on performance can emerge indirectly. In the analysis, OCB acts as a full mediator, bridging the relationship between commitment and performance. In other words, as employee commitment to the organization increases, they are more motivated to engage in extra-role behaviors, thus making their contribution to performance more tangible. Based on these findings, strengthening organizational culture needs to be implemented in a more targeted and sustainable manner. AKHLAK values, as the basis for work behavior, need to be internalized through various organizational activities such as case discussions, coaching from unit leaders, and improving leadership role models in daily life. Cultural alignment is also important to measure objectively, for example by making it a behavioral indicator in the periodic performance appraisal system. Through this strategy, organizational culture becomes more than just a slogan, but truly lived and has a tangible impact on work quality. Encouraging employee commitment remains a crucial aspect that cannot be overlooked. Harmonious relationships between management

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and employees, attention to their well-being, and opportunities for growth will strengthen a sense of belonging to the organization. When commitment and OCB develop simultaneously, the work environment will become more supportive, collaborative, and rich in positive initiatives. Ultimately, the synergy of a strong culture, strong commitment, and high levels of OCB will create a solid foundation for improved employee performance and the company's continued success.

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